

EUREKA

European Knowledge Repository for Best Agricultural Practices

D6.9 – Impact Assessment Report: Participatory development of a project impact assessment framework

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History of Changes

Date	Changes
20.08.2022	<p>List of Figures: Figure 4 and Figure 8 added</p> <p>Section 2.2, a sentence added that the framework was really implemented: “Table 1 shows that the impact assessment framework was implemented in EUREKA.”</p> <p>Section 3.2 half a sentence added to explain how the four aspects are related to impact (rephrased from EUREKA’s CSA) “In WP1 of EUREKA, as per the project plan, specific indicators were developed for four aspects contributing to generate impact:”</p> <p>Section 3.2 Figure 4 added to accommodate the reviewers wish to refer more clearly to expected impacts “An overview of societal needs, EUREKA’s goals, the four aspects contributing to impact and EUREKA’s expected impacts is given in Figure 5 below.”</p> <p>Same section Figure 4 added Figure 1 – Societal needs, EUREKA’s goals, the four aspects contributing to impact and EUREKA’s expected impacts</p> <p>Same section, reference to Figure 4 added and additional explanation of the four aspects added: “For EUREKA, these goals are testing the feasibility of an EU-wide central knowledge reservoir and knowledge-sharing platform (the EU FarmBook), developing ways to creating an active user community, and collecting feedback to improve the FarmBook in the future (see Figure 5). Project-specific indicators for EUREKA thus need to reflect this. The project-specific indicators were derived for the four aspects studied that contribute to generate impact:”</p> <p>Names of subsequent figures (Figures 5, 6 and 7 adapted)</p> <p>Section 4.2 sentence on expected spin-offs removed as this was not clear enough. Sentence on importance of positive uptake of MAP community added.</p> <p>“the MAP community receives the pilot version of the FarmBook positively, which is a pre-requisite to generate the expected impacts in the future (see Figure 8). The follow-up project, EU FarmBook 3.0, which was generated successfully based on the outcomes of EUREKA will help to achieve this”</p> <p>Same section, Figure 8 added: Figure 8 – Expected impacts, short-term impacts achieved and impacts to be achieved by the follow-up project EU FarmBook 3.0</p> <p>Same section, half a sentence added to better refer to expected impacts “an important step forward was taken to improve the long-term access to practical knowledge,”</p> <p>Section 5 text slightly rewritten and rearranged to better follow the order of expected impacts: “As the results of this impact assessment show, progress was achieved towards all three expected impacts, mapping and</p>

	<p>evaluation of H2020 projects, recommendations and technical specifications and collection of user feedback.</p> <p>Important learnings from the MAP analysis conducted by EUREKA could be integrated in the creation of the pilot version of the FarmBook. Increasing the sharing of MAP knowledge and practical information is much desired by the MAP community, yet it remains a challenging task.</p> <p>The code of the pilot version of the FarmBook is about to be published. Challenges arise from the desire to have interoperability between some of the existing databases and the EU FarmBook. Better interoperability will require projects coming together to discuss and agree on common standards, including a basic set of (open) metadata that will be adopted by collaborating partners. This conversation should also continue to involve the appropriate persons from the European Commission, especially from the EIP-AGRI Service Point. It is therefore recommended to continue the efforts of EUREKA to promote and exchange about FAIR data principles, IT standards and best practices. This will help to enable and enhance interoperability of existing databases and the future FarmBook through both technical approaches and social approaches, fostering collaboration between key actors and uptake by end-users.”</p> <p>Reference to the follow-up project EU FarmBook 3.0 added “The future for the EU FarmBook in terms of having a large and lasting positive impact on agriculture and forestry practices in Europe looks bright, also with the follow-up project EU FarmBook 3.0, which was acquired successfully based on the outcome of EUREKA.”</p>
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TASK 6.6

Summary

In Task 6.6, the impact assessment framework developed for the EUREKA project in Task 1.6 was applied. The framework for impact analysis was designed as an iterative and participative process within the EUREKA project to maximise the chance of being a successful project making an impact. This deliverable presents the outcome of the participatory development and use this project-specific impact assessment framework. The development started with an initial workshop in T6.1 and was completed in several steps. The impact assessment methods used comprised a mix of conceptual and qualitative methods, including a participatory impact-pathway approach and the co-creation of a project-specific set of indicators. Indicators were developed for four aspects of the EUREKA project: knowledge objects, the EU FarmBook as a knowledge reservoir, communication and dissemination of the FarmBook, and multi-actor (MA) involvement in the creation of the FarmBook. External actors and stakeholders (MA-community members and the EUREKA knowledge innovation panel, KIP) contributed to the impact-evaluation process, too, and provided input on the indicators developed and the approach itself. This deliverable presents the outcomes of this development process and application of the resulting indicators in the assessment of the impact of the EUREKA project. This report makes the results available to the MA-project (MAP) community and a larger public.

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

AKIS	Agricultural knowledge and innovation systems
CDE	Communication, dissemination and exploitation
D	Deliverable
EC	European Commission
EIP-AGRI	Agricultural European Innovation Partnership
FAIR	Findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable
GA	Grant Agreement
IPR	Intellectual property rights
KIP	Knowledge Innovation Panel
KoM	Kick-off meeting
MA	Multi-actor
MAA	Multi-actor approach
MAP	Multi-actor project
MOU	Memorandum of understanding
NGO	Non-governmental organization
NRN	National rural network
TN	Thematic Network
WP	Work Package
TX.X	Task X.X

1 Introduction

1.1 Project context

Knowledge and innovation are of vital importance for farmers and rural communities to meet the challenges of their everyday work in securing food production sustainably in a world undergoing rapid change, e.g., due to climate change, demographic change and digitalisation. Multi-actor projects (MAPs) are characterized by an interactive innovation format based on co-creation of actors with complementary expertise all along the project duration. With this interactive innovation format, the EU research and innovation framework programme Horizon 2020, the largest-ever European funding programme for research and innovation that ran from 2014 to 2020, has resulted in a large number of research projects working to transform knowledge into innovative solutions to meet societal needs. Also, in the current programme Horizon Europe (2021-2027), the European Commission (EC) puts co-creation of impact to meet societal needs up front (EC 2018). Previous research has shown that agricultural knowledge and innovation systems (AKIS) and research networks have created multiple additional links between AKIS actors (farmers, foresters, advisors, researchers, non-governmental organisations (NGOs), networks etc.; EC 2019, EU SCAR AKIS 2019). These networks and links differ in quality and vitality between EU regions. The European Innovation Partnership 'Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability' (EIP-AGRI) has an open-innovation concept (van Oost 2017). Following the MA approach, it is aimed at making best use of complementary types of knowledge and facilitating broader and faster diffusion of innovative solutions in practice by promoting collaboration of different types of actors, e.g., scientific researchers with agricultural advisors and practitioners.

There is a need to improve knowledge flows from MAP, where knowledge for societal needs is co-created, to a greater number of practitioners like farmers, foresters and other rural businesses. The EU-wide agricultural knowledge base can be strengthened and reinforced by developing an open source e-platform for sharing innovative practical knowledge. This open-source knowledge platform should be a two-sided, interactive environment that will address the needs and improve the connections between two distinct user groups: MAP partners and MA end-users (farmers, foresters, advisors, scientists, policy makers...).

The main aim of the EUREKA project is to test the feasibility of such an open-data knowledge by developing a pilot version, which the project has named the EU FarmBook. This work includes finding approaches to stimulate the formation of an active MA community to promote use of the EU FarmBook and to collect user feedback to continually improve the platform in the future.

The desired impact of such a unique EU knowledge repository is that results of MAP can be spread quickly to all actors of AKIS in all regions, providing them with up-to-date technological and scientific information for a more knowledge-based agricultural and forestry system. This can lead to improved knowledge flows between actors and regions and stronger links between research and practice. Therefore, the expected impacts of the EUREKA project on the longer term, by building and testing the pilot version of the EU FarmBook, are (1) increased sharing of MAP know-how and spreading of practical information, (2) recommendations and technical specifications for greater interoperability and integration of European or member states' knowledge bases and (3) improved long-term access to practical knowledge co-created by MAP.

1.2 EUREKA project concept

An overview of the concept and methodology of the EUREKA project is given in Figure 2. In EUREKA's WP1 (MA knowledge mapping and co-creating MA best practices), MA knowledge supply was analysed

and best practices were collected. The EUREKA project conducted a feasibility study on creating an open-source knowledge repository based on best practices by analysing end-user needs and preferences with a persona approach, stimulating an active MA community, engaging end-users and collecting feedback to improve and promote use of the FarmBook in the future.

An interactive process of impact assessment at several key points of the project was developed based on best practices, which facilitated co-defining main challenges, co-creation of impact assessment indicators, refinement of indicators and application of these indicators in the project. This impact report integrates main recommendations from two deliverables of the EUREKA project: Deliverable 1.1 (Map of all MA projects by sector and macro region with links to the EIP-AGRI landscape) and Deliverable 1.8 (MA encyclopedia & participative set of indicators) and makes them available to the MA community. In the development and assessment process, external feedback from end-users regarding intermediate results from the Knowledge Innovation Panel (KIP) and also the Strategic Innovation Board (SIB; see Deliverable 6.7) was taken into account. This report reflects results of WP1 (Knowledge mapping and co-creating best practices, and here specifically T1.6, ‘Developing a framework for impact assessment and providing guidance how to best design future MAP to maximize their impact’) and WP6 (EUREKA co-ordination and management, and here specifically T6.6, ‘Applying the impact framework developed in T1.6 to maximize the impact of EUREKA’).

Figure 2 – Concept and Methodology of the EUREKA project

2 EUREKA impact assessment methodology

2.1 Impact assessment approach and framework development

Various methods are used for impact assessment in agricultural research and innovation projects. Weißhuhn et al. (2018) describe that different conceptual, qualitative or quantitative, or a mix of these methods are used. Conceptual methods imply the development of concepts or frameworks for impact assessment; qualitative methods use qualitative data, e.g., text-based material from surveys or the collection of feedback; quantitative methods use quantitative data. Douthwaite et al. (2017) developed the concept of a participatory impact pathway analysis, which meets the requirements of the open-innovation concept of EIP-AGRI and seems to fit very well in the open research and innovation environment of MAP. Also, Horizon Europe makes use of an ‘impact-pathway’ concept that links project results to project outputs and finally to expected impacts. The aim is to foster clearly-described and project-specific pathways to maximize impact and innovation (Mazzucato 2018). Participatory impact pathway analysis uses logic maps, which link input – via output and outcome – to impact, and supports participatory processes with multiple types of actors (Douthwaite et al. 2017).

In the EUREKA project, participatory pathway analysis was used on two levels. Firstly, in the analysis of best practices of MAP in WP 1 of EUREKA, e.g., in a workshop with MAP coordinators. Secondly, on a project level for the EUREKA project. The purpose of using a participatory approach to impact analysis in the project was to involve the project team in finding the best way to maximise impact and to activate each team member to contribute to EUREKA’s impact with their specific expertise and strengths.

It is important to manage and monitor the success and impact of MAP. To facilitate this, indicators of H2020 were developed to monitor and assess results and impacts of specific actions (see D6.7, section 2.1). In this context, *output*, *outcome*, *impact*, and *impact indicators* are defined as follows: **Outputs** are products and services which result from a project – thus outcome corresponds to what a project does and offers. **Outcomes** are the project’s results at the target-group level. They illustrate what positive changes the project intends to bring about within the target group. Desired changes at the societal level are designated as **Impact**. These can include changes in the society’s social and economic conditions. **Impact indicators** in H2020 play an important role as they “represent what the successful outcome should be in terms of impact on the economy/society beyond those directly affected by the intervention” (EC 2015, p. 6). So, they measure “outcome ... in terms of impact” and are used as impact indicators with a focus on effects beyond the direct and immediate sphere of influence of the project, as opposed to output indicators which are related to individual deliverables, or result indicators giving a picture of immediate effects taking the direct participants of the intervention into account (EC 2015, p.6).

In the same document it is also stated that “reliable indicators of results and impacts are limited,” one of the reasons being the time lag between project inputs and the outcomes and impacts of the intervention (EC 2015, p. 5), which usually become visible some time after the intervention has ended. So the terminology “indicators for outcome ... in terms of impact” reflects the tension between operationalized indicators in relation to impact, and the prediction of actual post-project impact beyond the sphere of influence of the project in terms of time and people. In this impact report, outcome in terms of impact is assessed post-hoc, i.e., shortly after the end of the funding period of the project (31-March-2022).

Reliable and useful impact assessment of a given project typically implies that the project was designed for impact from the start by embedding a culture of impact (assessment) (Blundo-Canto et

al. 2019). In EUREKA this was achieved through a structured sequence of impact assessment activities conducted with the project team throughout the duration of the project. Douthwaite et al. (2017) describe two important trends in agricultural innovation projects, both of which highlight an increasing need for complexity-aware approaches: An increasing awareness of interventions taking place in complex systems, and increasing insistence of funding agencies to achieve quantifiable targets. Co-creation and co-development with multiple actor types is an example of such a complexity-aware approach (Douthwaite et al. 2017).

In MAPs, impact assessment is best organized as an ongoing interactive MA process throughout the project. The main goal throughout the process is to keep all team members actively involved in co-creation of impact using their specific expertise and to constantly align and refine aims during the project. The framework for impact assessment in EUREKA, which was co-created in WP 1, reflects this stepwise process (Figure 3). This framework is based on Deliverable 1.8 and Task (T)1.6, and is meant to show the stepwise process of co-creation of the impact assessment framework.

Figure 3 – Impact assessment framework co-created for the EUREKA project resulting from WP1

2.2 Implementation of the impact assessment framework

The framework developed aims to show that throughout the project there were interactive activities and feedback sessions to implement the impact assessment framework, from the initial development of impact indicators to the actual impact-related data collection and analysis. An overview of the activities during the project meetings and online collaboration phases starting from the Grant Agreement (GA) and Kick-off meeting (KoM) is given in Table 1 below. **Table 1 shows that the impact assessment framework was implemented in EUREKA.**

Table 1 – Overview of activities related to the impact assessment framework throughout the EUREKA project

Document or Meeting and Date	Actors involved	Activities
Step 1. Preliminary set of indicators		
GA / 18 09 2019	All consortium members	Finalizing GA
Step 2. Shared understanding of main challenges		
GA / 18 09 2019	All consortium members	Finalizing GA
KoM / 27-29 01 2020	All consortium members, a few KIP / SIB members, Policy Officer and Project Officer	Project meeting, discussion of aims
Step 3. Shared understanding of objectives, outcome, impact		
KoM / 27-29 01 2022	All consortium members, a few KIP / SIB members, Policy Officer and Project Officer	Project meeting, logic map activities
Step 4. Iterative development of indicators		
KIP-meeting / 16 02 2021	All consortium members, KIP members (more than 20), Project Officer	Online meeting, reverse brainstorming & feedback session
Mid-term meeting / 15 & 17 06 2021	All consortium members	Online meeting, work session collecting learnings and discussion of formats
Step 5. Shared tailored impact indicators		
Fall meeting 2021 / 21 10 2021	All consortium members	Online meeting, digital canvas session, voting and finalizing indicators
Step 6. Application of impact indicators		
Final project meeting / 24 03 2022	All consortium members	Online meeting, discussion of indicators and their implementation in CDE reporting
Co-creation of D6.9 / M03 & M04 2022	T1.6 and T6.6 members with support of many consortium members	Online meeting and co-creation of deliverable
Step 7. Co-creation of impact beyond project		
Final outreach event / 29 03 2022	(MAP) researchers, advisors and farmers' organizations, policymakers/decision-makers, and consortium members	Online meeting, panel discussion
FarmBook 3.0	Consortium of the follow-up project FarmBook 3.0, other MAPs and their networks	Follow-up project

How the impact assessment framework co-created by the EUREKA team was implemented in the EUREKA project along the project timeline is depicted in Figure 4 below.

Figure 4 – Application of the impact assessment framework to the EUREKA project

3 Co-creation of the EUREKA impact assessment indicators

3.1 Integration of WP 1 findings

Based on an analysis of more than 100 multi-actor projects, one of the main findings of Deliverable 1.1 (Map of all MA projects by sector and macro region with links to the EIP-AGRI landscape) was that there is an excellent network for research in Europe. However, the results also showed that these networks differ in connectivity and strength between EU macro-regions (Western, Eastern, Northern, Southern). The main recommendations of this mapping study of MAPs are related to the powerful effect of networks on enhancing uptake of project results and strengthening knowledge flows. Specifically, it was recommended:

- to highly promote networking between Eastern European countries and those in the other parts,
- to enhance networking in all of Europe through MA activities, and
- to link to and to address national and regional rural networks.

These findings and recommendations were integrated in EUREKA activities through providing translation options for non-English speaking target groups, and through indicators that encourage networking activities with partners of the MA community and national or regional networks.

The review of MAPs and interviews with members of the MAP community revealed important findings and recommendations on best practices regarding impact assessment in MA projects. Deliverable 1.8 (MA encyclopedia and participative set of impact indicators) summarizes the following recommendations:

- a tailored, interactive, project-specific method of impact assessment with a limited number of suitable impact indicators should be used; the impact evaluation should be performed as an interactive MA process
- the indicators should comprise a mix of qualitative and quantitative indicators and should be customized to project-specific goals
- the impact assessment process should comprise external and internal impact evaluation steps during the course of the project

The tailored, interactive and project-specific method was accommodated in EUREKA by the impact assessment framework developed for the project (see Figure 4). A more limited set of indicators targeted at promotion and improvement of the FarmBook was obtained in a collaborative process for the aspects of MAP investigated in WP1 (see section below). Indicators selected comprise quantitative and qualitative indicators. External and internal impact assessment were achieved by collecting feedback from end-users during the KIP meeting (Month 14) and feedback of participants of national events (Months 26-27). This process is explained further in the next section.

3.2 EUREKA impact indicators

Impact indicators in H2020 projects “represent what the successful outcome should be in terms of impact on the economy/society beyond those directly affected by the intervention” (EC 2015, p. 6). MAP usually define a preliminary set of project-specific impact indicators in the GA, which are matching the call and its underlying societal challenge. This is prepared in the conceptualisation and initialisation phase of the project. In WP1 of EUREKA, as per the project plan, specific indicators were developed for four aspects **contributing to generate impact**: (1) project output/knowledge objects in T1.2, (2) knowledge reservoirs in T1.3, (3) communication and dissemination in T1.4 and (4) MA involvement in T1.5. The impact assessment was designed to monitor the outcome in terms of impact as envisaged by the EUREKA team when the indicators were developed.

The starting point was the preliminary list of indicators in the GA, which was discussed during the KoM, then developed further in WP1 (based on findings of MAP analysis and interviews) and in several subsequent project meetings. **An overview of societal needs, EUREKA’s goals, the four aspects contributing to impact and EUREKA’s expected impacts is given in Figure 5 below.** The approach was to tailor and refine the preliminary set of impact indicators over the course of the project interactively with all actors, and to apply the final set of indicators in the impact assessment process to enhance the overall impact of the project by actively involving all team members with their specific knowledge and expertise. For example, for CDE activities, a set of eight indicators of the GA was specified into a set of four tailored indicators supporting the process of reaching EUREKAs goals.

External feedback on the impact analysis is important to integrate diverse knowledge and expertise from outside the project consortium. The term *impact analysis* here refers broadly to the process of designing a project for impact, interactive development of indicators, and the subsequent application of the tailored indicators developed. External feedback was collected in two main ways: via obtaining feedback regarding the process and the indicators from KIP members, and via adding end-user

feedback collected during the national events of individual EUREKA partners to the list of indicators.

Figure 5 – Societal needs, EUREKA's goals, the four aspects contributing to impact and EUREKA's expected impacts

The feedback from the KIP was received through an interactive work session with KIP members and EUREKA project team members before finalizing the list of indicators. External feedback regarding the knowledge repository developed (the pilot version of the EU FarmBook) and the envisaged MA approach to maintain the EU FarmBook longer-term was obtained from participants of the national webinars.

One of the findings of research on best practices from WP 1, T1.6 regarding impact assessment in MAPs was that indicators should be customized to project-specific goals. For EUREKA, these goals are testing the feasibility of an EU-wide central knowledge reservoir and knowledge-sharing platform (the EU FarmBook), developing ways to creating an active user community, and collecting feedback to improve the FarmBook in the future (see Figure 5). Project-specific indicators for EUREKA thus need to reflect this. The project-specific indicators were derived for the four aspects studied that contribute to generate impact:

1. The quality and quantity of knowledge objects available in the EU FarmBook
2. The performance and usefulness of the EU FarmBook as a knowledge repository
3. Communication and dissemination of the EU FarmBook
4. A multi-actor approach to building, populating and maintaining the EU FarmBook

For these four aspects, indicators were specified for the EUREKA project and then finalized with project team members in the interactive impact session in fall 2021. A list of these project-specific indicators resulting from this process is given in Table 2. Each of the four aspects examined in WP1 for the 101 MAP was specified for the EUREKA project as follows:

- Indicators for knowledge objects (KOs) refer to KO considered significant for the development of the FarmBook. Analysis of best practices showed that KOs facilitating uptake of results were

considered very valuable, intellectual property rights (IPR) documents and guides were mentioned as best practice. During the development of the FarmBook, it became apparent that especially the introduction of FAIR and open data principles is an ongoing process and will have an impact on KOs uploaded and shared in the FarmBook. A guide regarding FAIR open data seems to be useful in the following steps of further development and promotion of the FarmBook. This is why KOs such as standards, IPR documents or how-to guides on the annotation of KOs, or the production of FAIR data, were considered relevant.

- As EUREKA is a feasibility study exploring what it takes to developing and populate the EU FarmBook with high-quality KOs, it was discussed that important target users at this stage are the MAP community and consultants as well as contact persons of national and regional knowledge networks.
- Indicators for user feedback were both quantitative and qualitative, especially the qualitative feedback was considered important for the future development of the FarmBook. Networking-related indicators, such as links to other projects that are building or operating open-source databases, or contact efforts of other projects to link with EUREKA/EU FarmBook, reflect the importance of networking to promote results to a wider public.
- Efforts of joint activities with other MAP or networks were considered key to project success, as networking with other projects including thematic networks (TN), national rural networks (NRN) or other networks can efficiently boost knowledge flow – an important learning from the mapping of MAP in EUREKAs WP 1. This is why indicators for networking activities were included in the list for CDE activities. The indicators also covered social media activities, as they were part of best practice narratives regarding CDE, where MAP representatives reported that social media provide means to reach very high numbers of people efficiently.
- Indicators for the MAA included quantitative and qualitative aspects of MA involvement and feedback, including the number of activities, diversity of actors, and number of people reached. In the current situation, for the MAA, the consortium decide that at this stage of development of the FarmBook the target group should match the current status of the EU FarmBook as a pilot version, i.e. the target group should be mainly the MA community and consultants rather than a larger community of practitioners. Also for the same reason at this stage broad qualitative feedback rather than quantitative feedback should be collected from a diverse group of actors.

Figure 6 illustrates the discussion and collaborative refinement of the indicators for the knowledge repository of EUREKA (i.e., the EU FarmBook and its database) and CDE activities set up to promote uptake and use of the (pilot version of the) FarmBook. The figure shows EUREKA's intended impacts related to the knowledge repository (FarmBook, top) and CDE activities to promote the FarmBook (bottom). The aspects are given in yellow boxes, indicators in green boxes, examples given by consortium partners are given in blue boxes, and alternatives/new suggestions in red boxes.

Figure 6 – Collaborative refinement of EUREKA impact indicators for two aspects: knowledge repository (the FarmBook) and CDE activities (to promote the FarmBook)

The list of EUREKA’s project-specific impact indicators, co-created during the mid-term meeting and taking input of the KIP members into account, then finalized in fall 2021, is presented in Table 2 below.

Table 2 – List of impact indicators developed for the EUREKA project

Impact indicators	Data required
Aspect 1. Knowledge objects	
IPR documents	Number of IPR documents
How-to-guides	Number of guides
Standards	Number of standards
Aspect 2. The EU FarmBook platform	
Involvement of target users in creation of FarmBook	Share of different target user groups in key events e.g. number of national webinars to present FarmBook, number of user tests
Collection and sharing of user feedback	User feedback (e.g. from user tests and national webinars), share of positive feedback (qualitative), suggestions for improvement (qualitative), number of user tests
Links to open data sources (e.g., other projects' knowledge reservoirs)	Collection of contact details of projects which contacted FarmBook
Number of people/projects contacting FarmBook	Collection of contact details of projects which contacted FarmBook
Number of presentations given in workshops/study days	Number of webinars/presentations in workshops/study days and size of audience
Aspect 3. CDE	
Joint activities with other MA projects	Number of joint activities with other MAP/TN
Outreach with focus on practitioners	Number of activities, number of audience/people reached
Outreach to networks	Number of activities, number of audience
Activities on social media	Number of activities, number of people reached
Aspect 4. MA approach	
Involvement of MA throughout project	GA, type of actors involved at key events (e.g. KoM and KIP), share of positive feedback
Collection, evaluation and sharing of feedback on network effects	Number of activities, type and number of people reached

4 EUREKA Impact assessment results

4.1 Impact assessment results

The indicators developed for the EUREKA project were implemented in the CDE monitoring of EUREKA in January 2022. EUREKA's project impact monitoring data were used to collect information about CDE activities from all partners. The data collected and reported here represent self-reported data of EUREKA consortium members. To facilitate the collection of end-user feedback from the national webinars to promote the pilot version of the EU FarmBook, forms with questions to discuss with participants were provided to all consortium members prior to these events. These forms were also used by consortium members to report on the national events, including as a basis for the assessment of the qualitative feedback of participants.

Results of the impact assessment are given in Table 3 and discussed in the following section.

Table 3 – Results of the impact assessment

Impact indicators	Assessment results
Aspect 1. Knowledge objects	
IPR documents (1)	First version of a Memorandum of Understanding (MOU) for data transfer to the EU FarmBook
How-to-guides (3)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. User manual for upload of knowledge objects to the EU FarmBook (LINK) 2. Upload video (LINK) 3. User manual for the EU FarmBook (LINK; see also D4.4)
Standards	Use of existing data standards and librarian standards achieved (see D3.3 and D4.3)
Aspect 2. FarmBook	
Involvement of target users in creation of FarmBook	End user tests with farmers, foresters and advisors (19 tests across 4 macro-regions). Dissemination Workshops with MAP community, researchers, farmers and foresters were reached via national events
Collection and sharing of user feedback	User feedback collected from >1,150 participants in 57 national events and 19 in-depth user tests
Links to open data sources (e.g., other projects' knowledge reservoirs)	Discussions with other projects initiated and records of interactions kept
Number of projects contacting FarmBook	14 H2020 MAP, 7 TN, 1 NRN, 6 other
Number of presentations given in workshops/study days	More than 60 workshops/presentations, more than 1,150 people reached in partners' national events (Feb-Mar 2022)
Aspect 3. CDE	
Joint activities with other MA projects	16 (EURAKNOS, LIAISON, IOF, i2connect, ROSEWOOD; see D5.5)
Outreach with focus on practitioners	14 activities, about 680 people reached
Outreach to networks	39, about 8070 people reached
Activities on social media	20, more than 46000 people reached
Aspect 4. MA approach	
Involvement of MA	Involvement of KIP/SIB throughout project (see Table 1) Involvement of MA throughout project (see Figure 2)
Collection, evaluation and sharing of feedback on network effects	13 activities for farmers, foresters and advisors, as well as MAP actors and scientific community, more than 3000 people reached, about half of these farmers, foresters and advisors

The evaluation of the data collected regarding involvement of target users in the creation of the EU FarmBook (indicator for Aspect 2) shows that end users were actively involved throughout the project, especially during the study of end-user needs and preferences. This study included different user types from different countries, see Figure 7. Based on this study, the user personas were created to aid in the development of the pilot version of the platform (see Deliverable 2.3, 'Online digital kit

with MA end-user archetypes and end-user journeys'). The data in **Figure 7** is based on user tests for Nordic-Baltic and Mediterranean regions.

Figure 7 – End-user types of the personas created for the development of the FarmBook and end-user types in user tests reflecting different types of end-users studied in WP2 to make the FarmBook user-friendly.

One of the findings of WP1 (MA knowledge mapping and co-creating MA best practices) was that a mix of both qualitative and quantitative indicators provides more useful insights than using quantitative indicators alone. Quantitative indicators have the advantage that they are easier to work with, but their usefulness depends highly on, e.g., the question being asked, the value being measured and how it was measured. Qualitative indicators can be very useful in the early stages of research, as they allow for more flexible answers that can help to reveal overall trends or gaps that help to identify define further research steps with more quantitative approaches. This applies to the EUREKA project, as it is an early-stage or “pilot version” of the EU FarmBook knowledge repository being developed. This is why broad feedback was collected and evaluated qualitatively, e.g. from participants of the KoM, the KIP meeting, and participants of the national webinars to introduce the FarmBook. One of the main aims of collecting and evaluating feedback was to improve the platform in the future, so feedback was analysed qualitatively to capture suggestions for improvement. An overview of qualitative aspects of feedback is given below.

Another important finding of the evaluation of best practices was that the impact assessment process should comprise external and internal impact evaluation steps during the course of the project. Internal feedback regarding the approach on impact assessment in the EUREKA project was collected, e.g., during the KoM. During the KoM, impact expectations were discussed by project team members in several interactive sessions. There was wide agreement on the main objectives and intended impact from the start. Also, the participatory impact pathway approach obtained good support. In discussions it became apparent that the main intention this approach was well understood, as illustrated by reactions of a project team members who stated that the logic map activity FarmBook co-creation process by all project team members by allowing them to having a say from the beginning of the project.

External feedback was obtained from KIP members near the mid-term of the EUREKA project in an online workshop. KIP members present were researchers from other MAP projects, multipliers,

advisors, farmers and others. During an interactive session of the meeting focused on impact evaluation, KIP members were asked to give feedback on indicators and discuss findings of WP 1. There was strong agreement and support among KIP members for a project-specific approach to impact assessment.

The external feedback of end-users at the end-user tests (19 in 4 regions) and the webinars (numbering 57 in total between the different EUREKA partners) was gathered qualitatively and semi-quantitatively.

The general idea of having a sustainable open knowledge repository for all MAP results and of creating a cooperative memory of results of research in Europe was supported widely by participants. The opportunities for exchange and dialogue with experts (through voluntary “Expert” users of /contributors to the EU FarmBook) and other users of the platform (“Community” pages) were welcomed very much. Also, the idea of enabling direct sharing of information by practitioners was strongly supported by participants. The feedback evaluated covers at least 1,150 participants, which represented different actors: About half of the participants were advisors, about one quarter were members of the MAP community (see [Figure 8](#)). The distribution of participants over different actor groups shows that different types of actors, including end-users and multipliers, were reached in the webinars.

Figure 8 – Distribution of participants of the national webinars across different actor groups estimated based on feedback reports of 30 webinars covering about 600 participants.

Feedback was also collected about the user experiences and user needs for the follow-up project, based on a live demonstration plus hands-on testing session both from the end-users at end-user tests and the participants of the national webinars. The user interface received very positive feedback for being visually attractive and easy to use. Among the functionalities of the platform, translation was experienced to be the most useful. Being able to access information in the national language was of key importance for a large number of participants in the end-user tests and of the national events from many countries. Providing translation options helps bridging gaps between regions and user groups.

Suggestions for improvements or changes to the platform included improvement of (automatic) translations and of the set of pictures that appear next to each individual knowledge object, which

sometimes do not reflect the contents of the categories well enough. Additional features considered as useful are the interoperability/linkage to existing databases, such as open science databases, existing EU databases, national agricultural research network databases or thematic databases. This shows that participants of the webinars consider the FarmBook as a potential solution to simplify storage and sharing of knowledge by creating a single European one-for-all knowledge repository that facilitates access for users from different countries through translation. Some of the participants pointed out that it is of utmost importance to communicate the added value of an EU-wide open knowledge repository very clearly. The social functions provide additional benefit and can help to convince sceptical end-users that the FarmBook is not “just another database”. Many of the participants expressed that it might be difficult to convince project teams to fulfil additional reporting requirements for yet another database. Nearly 20 databases were mentioned by webinar participants. Future research can show whether it is useful to link (some of) these databases to the FarmBook. Linkages to existing databases and technical solutions regarding interoperability or single upload have the potential to improve the acceptability of the FarmBook.

Another noteworthy suggestion from participants was that more in-depth training might be required to get to know the features and functions of the EU FarmBook pilot version better, and thereby to be able to use it well. Training should allow for differences in users’ ability to use digital tools and should be sensitive to issues related to inaccuracies in automatic translations. This should also be considered in development of training material for the future versions of the EU FarmBook. Furthermore, participants stressed the importance of practical knowledge in easily understandable language and of direct relevance for end users (which cannot be achieved by translation alone).

As the EUREKA project is a feasibility study, it has a special character. This is why, in the impact assessment process, special emphasis was given to the co-creative process of impact generation and assessment, as well as the collection of user feedback after hands-on testing of the EU FarmBook pilot version. The application of the impact indicators developed shows that the project performed well, especially in addressing technical and social challenges of the development of the pilot platform. The EUREKA project provides recommendations for data governance (see D3.3), technical specifications for greater interoperability and integration of European and member states’ knowledge bases (see D3.2) and improved long-term access to practical knowledge produced (see D3.3). Also, a first version of a formal Memorandum of Understanding (MOU) for the data transfer to the FarmBook has been set-up to facilitate uptake of the FarmBook going forward. The collection and analysis of the user feedback will be used to continually improve the platform in the future. Through this focus on user feedback, the impact assessment process helps to form a bridge between EUREKA and the follow-up work to be continued in EU FarmBook.

4.2 Key learnings

The main aim of the EUREKA project was to test the feasibility of developing an EU-level online knowledge repository (the EU FarmBook) in a co-creative process. The project was set up in a way that facilitates interactive approaches to involve the MAP community in the development and promotion of the FarmBook to help insure that information is transferred to those actors who need to use it. Douthwaite et al. (2017) describe three impact pathways, which have their equivalents in the EUREKA project: The technology development and adoption pathway corresponds to the development of the FarmBook in EUREKA. The capacity development pathway is equivalent to building capacity to create a user- and impact-oriented knowledge platform, e.g. by using personas in EUREKA. Likewise, the policy influence pathway corresponds to promoting the FarmBook among policy makers and collecting feedback from the EUREKA Strategic Innovation Board.

The main aim of EUREKA was achieved by developing a pilot version of the EU FarmBook, making use of personas and MA user testing to achieve good fit with end-users needs and to create a user-friendly knowledge repository.

The MA community was actively involved in sharing best practices. Desired impact was actively refined in a MA process continuously throughout the project. External and internal feedback was collected and integrated in the process of impact evaluation to gather valuable information to improve the future versions of the FarmBook. Networking activities with other MAPs, TNs, national and rural networks were included in the list of indicators, and networking activities were performed to make best use of links to other projects and networks and to achieve high impact.

The main learnings regarding the process of impact assessment itself are that monitoring impact, and/or assessing output in terms of impact beyond the project duration, is especially challenging in such a complex and short-duration project. However, even though project duration was short, there are indications that **the MAP community receives the pilot version of the FarmBook positively, which is a pre-requisite to generate the expected impacts in the future (see Figure 8). The follow-up project, EU FarmBook 3.0, which was generated successfully based on the outcomes of EUREKA will help to achieve this.**

Figure 9 – Expected impacts, short-term impacts achieved and impacts to be achieved by the follow-up project EU FarmBook 3.0

A key lesson regarding dissemination of the pilot version of the EU FarmBook is the importance and challenge of setting and managing the expectations of potential users and contributors. Given that EUREKA was still principally a feasibility study, with the FarmBook platform still in a relatively early stage of development, it was crucial to strike the right balance between raising awareness and excitement about the pilot version and the *potential* of an EU-wide platform on one hand, with a clear presentation of the current 'pilot' state of the FarmBook and the challenges that lie ahead on the other. However, the main aim of successfully proving the concept was achieved, an important step forward was taken **to improve the long-term access to practical knowledge**, and reactions and feedback of participants showed that the main ideas of the FarmBook were made visible.

Participants' feedback also helped to identify the future technical challenge of interoperability of national repositories and a European repository. Aspects to consider are, amongst others, differences in level of completion and size, type and ontology of knowledge objects, and quality of metadata. Data and feedback collected already provide some information on which repositories are most promising to link up with the EU FarmBook and could be engaged.

Main learnings regarding the social aspects and perceptions surrounding the FarmBook are that it is received positively; many participants of the webinars inquired directly about possibilities to upload knowledge objects. The advantage of co-creating a common memory of European agricultural and forestry research projects that allows easy sharing and access of information was stressed by participants of all user groups addressed. Co-creation through a structured sequence of impact activities along the project duration was experienced as a useful approach. However, discussions in response to midterm reporting show that qualitative results, e.g. in the form of best-practice reports or qualitative user feedback, might get dismissed as anecdotal if it is not explained well how key learnings can be derived for use in future projects (see Douthwaite et al. 2017).

User feedback also stressed that it remains an important task to make sure that practical knowledge is not only supplied in national languages, but also in easily understandable language. This means that the crafting of such texts and moderation of the knowledge repository are likely to require continued attention. Models for how to achieve this are therefore an important line of inquiry for the follow-up project.

Further learnings regarding social aspects are related to open data: The EU FarmBook not only introduces a knowledge repository, but also brings open data to the users of the platform. The process of introducing FAIR and open data principles in European agricultural research is ongoing and the introduction of the FarmBook can support this process by providing guidance and actively involving users.

5 Conclusions and recommendations

As the results of this impact assessment show, progress was achieved towards all three expected impacts, mapping and evaluation of H2020 projects, recommendations and technical specifications and collection of user feedback.

Important learnings from the MAP analysis conducted by EUREKA could be integrated in the creation of the pilot version of the FarmBook. Increasing the sharing of MAP knowledge and practical information is much desired by the MAP community, yet it remains a challenging task.

The code of the pilot version of the FarmBook is about to be published. Challenges arise from the desire to have interoperability between some of the existing databases and the EU FarmBook. Better interoperability will require projects coming together to discuss and agree on common standards, including a basic set of (open) metadata that will be adopted by collaborating partners. This conversation should also continue to involve the appropriate persons from the European Commission, especially from the EIP-AGRI Service Point. It is therefore recommended to continue the efforts of EUREKA to promote and exchange about FAIR data principles, IT standards and best practices. This will help to enable and enhance interoperability of existing databases and the future FarmBook through both technical approaches and social approaches, fostering collaboration between key actors and uptake by end-users.

The feedback from early users on the pilot version of the EU FarmBook is largely positive; end users from all groups perceive the need and see the benefits of better sharing of knowledge among actors in farming, forestry and rural communities. Reactions of users also showed that the dual character of the FarmBook (i.e., knowledge repository plus social functions) is highly appreciated and makes the platform more attractive to potential end-users. Solutions providing social functions like direct contact to experts or extensive translation options will increase the attractiveness of the future EU FarmBook.

Language is of key importance. This aspect also refers to the quality of the translation, which is crucial to making knowledge objects findable. Technical innovation will enable wider use of automatic translation options in the future, which will increase the usability of the FarmBook, especially in regions and end-user groups with a strong preference for their native language.

The objective of modernising farming and forestry by digitalisation, knowledge sharing, and innovation is a longer-term process. Making use of networks at different scales (including AKIS coordination points, national and regional levels) and efforts to better connect actors are helpful to promote the FarmBook to a wider public. Continued efforts should be taken to ensure sufficient practice-orientation of the majority of the knowledge objects in the EU FarmBook database and the crafting of materials in a way that they meet the needs of practitioners. Special focus should be placed on training materials, which should be developed for diverse user groups.

The future for the EU FarmBook in terms of having a large and lasting positive impact on agriculture and forestry practices in Europe looks bright, also with the follow-up project EU FarmBook 3.0, which was acquired successfully based on the outcome of EUREKA. Stimulating discussions with and feedback from a broad group of users provide valuable input for the tasks ahead. With continued co-creation and engagement among a diverse multi-actor community, the potential of this central knowledge platform can be realized.

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